

REVIEW ON THE USE OF NATURAL POLYMERS IN THE PROCESSING OF LEATHER

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ABSTRACT

The leather industry is a huge industry used in the conversion of skin and hides towards usable form. However, due to toxic chemical contents, it has great pollution abundance in the world. Previous studies deal with how biopolymers are used in each respective processing stage as cleaner technologies. However, there was little information about compressive research on bio-polymers in leather processing. So this paper uses Google Scholar for studies and to grasp information related to biopolymer applications. Innovations regarding the natural polymers' advantage in the leather processing stage solve the problem related to pollution. Among them, carbohydrates, protein and carbohydrates as soaking agents, keratin as unhairing agents, starch as tanning agents, starch and keratin as fillers, and keratin as finishing agents play a role in the processing stages. To sum up, this study focuses on the application of natural polymers in the leather processing industry.

Keywords: Natural Polymers; Leather Industry; Pollution; Cleaner Technology

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1. INTRODUCTION

Leather is a direct industrial product of natural skin. The architectural marvel of skin is yet unmatched by man-made synthetics. The comfort and personal hygiene of leather products have remained unique. Leather processing technology has evolved naturally from a traditional practice to an industrial activity. The leather industry contributes substantially to the pollution of the environment. Environmental challenges from leather processing arise from both the nature and the quantum of waste discharged [1]. As an alternative methodology natural polymers are used as processing chemicals in leather industries. Natural polymers are organic compounds that are found in nature and consist of repeated units called monomers.

These polymers can be derived from renewable sources such as plants, animals, and microorganisms. These natural polymers have gained significant interest in various industries including automotive, construction, and packaging. They serve as attractive reinforcement alternatives to synthetic fibres, offering several advantages. One of the key benefits of natural fibres is their ability to be extracted from renewable sources, making them a more sustainable option. Additionally, natural fibres are biodegradable, addressing the increasing environmental concerns caused by non-degradable plastics. In recent years, there have been advancements in organic and polymer chemistry, allowing for the development of new classes of bioactive polymers. Among them protein and carbohydrates used as soaking agents.[2], keratin used as unhairing agent, starch as tanning agent, keratin and starch as retaining agent and also keratin for finishing processing stage[3]. The main objective of this paper is to do compressive research on biopolymers in leather processing.

2. UNDERSTANDING LEATHER PROCESSING

Leather processing is a complex and intricate process that involves transforming animal hides into a durable and versatile material. Traditionally, this process has relied heavily on the use of chemical tanning agents derived from petroleum-based sources. However, with the growing concern for environmental sustainability, there has been a shift towards finding more eco-friendly alternatives.

2.1. Role of Natural Polymers Application in Leather Processing

Most researchers deal about natural polymers like protein and carbohydrates used as soaking agents, keratin used as unhairing agents, starch as tanning agent, keratin and starch as retanning agent and also keratin for finishing processing stage. In addition Chitosan, a natural polymer derived from chitin, has emerged as a promising candidate for leather processing. Chitosan is obtained from the exoskeletons of crustaceans such as shrimp, crab, and lobster, making it a renewable and abundant resource. Its molecular structure is similar to that of cellulose, a component of plant cell walls, giving chitosan several beneficial properties. Chitosan possesses excellent film-forming properties, which makes it suitable for creating a protective layer on leather surfaces. Chitosan also exhibits antimicrobial properties, making it an effective coating to prevent bacterial growth in leather [4]. In addition, chitosan has the ability to improve the mechanical properties of leather, making it softer and more flexible.

2.1.1 Soaking

Soaking is the first beam house processing stage have a role on rehydration of skin and removal of filth[5]. Due to high amount of salts during soaking much amount s of TDS are erupted to the environment[6]. As a remedy, natural polymers have been used to replace the salts to minimize TDS in waste water. Protein and carbohydrate release carbohydras and Protease enzyme and widely used for soaking [7, 8]. Here extraction of enzymes by bacterial action was applied and resulting greener soaking done by researchers.

2.1.2 Liming and Unhairing

Liming is the process which soaked hides and skins are treated with lime milk with or without the addition of sharpening agents like as sulphides, cyanides, amines, and so on to remove the hair, nail, and some interfibrillar soluble proteins particularly, mucins [8]. Polymers are being used to replace these chemicals since they are extremely hazardous and environmentally dangerous, contributing to excessive COD, BOD, TDS, SS, and other pollutants [9]. The most often utilized polymers alkaline proteas enzymes are vitally important to the existence of life itself. Enzymes are important in reducing both energy consumption and combating environmental pollution.

Enzymatic dehairing in tanneries has been envisaged as an alternative to sulfides [10]. Alkaline proteases can be used which enables the swelling of hair roots, and the subsequent attack of protease on the hair follicle protein allowing easy removal of the hair [11]. A large proportion of the known alkaline proteases are derived from microorganisms, especially *Bacillus* strains [12]. Enzymatic unhairing accomplished by proteolytic enzymes is of great commercial importance contributing to more than 40% of the world's commercially produced enzymes. Approximately 50% of the enzymes produced are used for industrial process [13]. Further, proteolytic enzymes are more efficient in enzymatic dehairing rather than amylolytic enzymes [13]. The enzymes cause loosening of the hair, without damaging the fibrous collagen of dermis.

The advantages of enzymatic dehairing are as follows:

- 1) significant reduction or even complete elimination of the use of sodium sulfide,
- 2) total recovery of hair resulting good quality with good saleable value, and
- 3) creation of an ecologically conducive atmosphere for the workers.

The chemical composition of fresh hides and skins falls approximately within the following limits: water 60- 65%; protein 25-30; fats 5-10% and small amounts of minerals. The chief entity of protein present in skin is collagen. Enzyme treated leather has shown better strength properties and greater surface area. Simplification of pre-tanning process by cutting down one-step viz bating. Americans have been practicing the sweating process for unhairing in which the depilation is being achieved by the combined actions of the enzymes of autolytic process and those are secreted by the bacterial species [14].

A great deal of work has been reported in the past, since 1960 employing enzymes for unhairing. However, the use of enzymes in the leather manufacturing process particularly for unhairing has not been accepted by the industry to the desired level. This is mainly because: a) enzymes are not effective enough to eliminate the sulfide, b) there is an apprehension that the enzymes assisted process needs stringent process control, and c) the cost of enzymes is not encouraging. Generally, Keratin protein has high degrees of cross-linking due to the presence of disulfide bonds, and hydrogen bonds and also due to hydrophobic interactions. Keratinases are capable of disrupting the highly stable keratin structure by destabilizing the di-sulphide bonds of recalcitrant keratin and as natural polymer it plays a role on unhairing industry [15]. *B. paralicheniformis* MKU3 is a potent producer of keratinase. *B. paralicheniformis* is believed to be one of the most important organisms in nature that can degrade keratin protein and prevent its accumulation over time [16]. The optimization of keratinase production by the organism and its capacity to hydrolyze feather keratin and dehair sheepskin was carried out and has proven to be highly efficient.

2.1.3 Tanning

Operation Regardless of the fact that chrome is a common tanning component in the manufacturing of all sorts of hides and skins over the world, it is a significant pollutant. In order to enhance chromium absorption or uptake through the tanning process, the de-pickled hides were pre-tanned with hyperbranched poly-amidoamine polymer (HPAM). The key factors that influence chrome tan exhaustion and fixing, such as shrinkage temperature of the tanned leather, were explored. The consequences revealed a considerable advancement in chrome exhaustion, shrinkage temperature, and the texture and softness of HPAM-treated leather. [17] introduced a new method for a chrome-free tanning process. The authors gave the tanning steps as pre-tanning with oxidized starch, tanning with titanium salt, neutralization, retanning, dyeing and finishing. The authors thought that pre-tanning with selectively oxidized starch enhanced the interaction of titanium with collagen and the leather had excellent texture and handle. [18] studied on modifying of corn starch by glutaraldehyde and used it in tanning process.

From the results they concluded that the modification of starch by glutaraldehyde was an efficient method to significantly improve its tanning property and the shrinkage temperature of the tanned leather was 85.2 °C. Accordingly, the authors thought that the modified starch could be used as a tanning agent and the pollution produced by chrome tanning could be significantly decreased.[19] studied on stabilization of collagen by dialdehyde starch (DAS). DAS samples were autoclaved before the tanning experiments. The authors specified that autoclaving of DAS was resulting hydrolysis to lower molecular weight oligomeric species. These lower molecular weight species showed better tanning properties compared to un-autoclaved DAS and similar effect was also observed on use of DAS in alkaline conditions. It was stated that the leather samples tanned with autoclaved dialdehyde starch at high pH values had shrinkage temperatures higher than 84 °C and the leathers exhibited high stability against collagenase.

Tanning ability of graft copolymer of phenols and starch with horseradish peroxidase (HRP) catalysis was investigated by [20].From the application results, the authors concluded that the phenols and starch graft copolymer had a good selective filling property and the retanned leather had an excellent thickening rate with higher shrinkage temperature. [21]synthesized a starch-polyacrylamide graft copolymer by means of HRP and graft copolymer was used in retanning process. From the evaluation of the results they have concluded that the increase of shrinkage temperature of the retanned leather proved that the graft copolymer played a certain role for wet blue, the thickness of retanned leather increased; also graft copolymer had a good selective filling property. It was also pointed out that the retanned leather had many advantages, including an excellent increased rate of thickness, good dyeing effect and eligible mechanical properties. [22]studied on graft copolymerization of oxidizing degradation of starch with acrylic acid, acrylonitrile and acrylamide as a leather retanning agent. They emphasized that the graft copolymer retanning had exceptional selective filling characteristics and could improve the uniformity of retanned leathers. It was also denoted that retanned leather had excellent softness, tightness and fullness, and its mechanical properties such as tensile, tear strength and elongation at break were improved. The authors also specified that the graft copolymer retanning will also be, biodegradable to some extent, and may reduce the environmental pollution caused by acrylic retans.

2.1.4 Re-tanning

Accordingly, the leather is treated in a second tanning process known as retanning and fatliquoring process to determine the required properties [23].Various retanning and fat liquoring agents with different characteristics are available to improve the final quality parameters of leathers according to the intended application. However, the properties generally desired from this type of materials are that it can be dissolved in water or dispersed, well penetrated into the collagen fiber, filling loosen parts within the fiber network homogeneously and being capable of bonding with the collagen reactive groups. Moreover, the expected qualifications of leathers to be improved by these chemicals include a tanning effect contributes to the thermal stability of leather, improved softness, elasticity, fullness, strength properties, light fastness, dyeability, water resistance, etc. A large number of chemicals are used simultaneously in the introduction of these properties to the leather, resulting in losses both in terms of waste load, time, and economy, and the desired performance cannot always be achieved due to chemical interactions. Different types of resins, polymeric products, vegetable and synthetic tannins, aldehyde derived products, natural and petroleum derivative fat liquors are being used in retanning/fat liquoring process[24] .These products are usually performed in a one single float which results in increased process duration, waste load with unbound chemicals and risk of interference between the chemicals leading to decreased performance properties. Besides, many retanning agents such as resin, synthetic tannins and aldehyde derived products have a potential to release free-formaldehyde into the leather matrix.

These retanning agents have also the disadvantage that they fix the leather fibers closely to one another, resulting in a reduction in flexibility. Accordingly, fat liquor is often used for softening, exerting a softening effect on the leather fibers by impregnation of the leather with oil. However, large quantities of fat liquor are required to make the leather sufficiently soft so that the leather becomes heavy and oily on its surface. For this reason, there is a great need for multifunctional technological products that reduce the number of chemicals used in leather production and environmental waste load, shorten process times and improve the properties of the leather. On the other hand, lubricating polymers are a good alternative to combine a pronounced softening effect with softening and retanning features, which are evenly distributed over the structure of the hide or skin.

Natural Polymeric softeners can help to simplify wet-end applications by reducing the amount and number of traditional lubricating, retanning and softening agents required. In recent years there has been an increasing interest in the design of bio-polymers for various applications in many industries and many end products including foods, drugs, cosmetics, and so on. Gelatinous products are the subgroups obtained from collagen which is one of the most interesting degradable polymers [25]. Collagen hydrolysates and collagen peptides are new forms yielded by hydrolysis of native collagen having lower molecular weight fragments than original structure and including a wide range of subcategories with differentiated functionalities. Collagen hydrolysates as natural biopolymer exhibit superior properties such as higher enthalpy, the greater network structure of fibrils and strong reactive complex in the leather production. Castor oil, vegetable-based fat liquor finds many industrial applications as a natural surface-active agent with good foaming performance, emulsification and wetting ability, excellent softening properties and used in different formulas for fat liquoring process (Ma et al. 2017b). In the leather production hydrogenated castor oil was especially preferred to avoid yellowing problem on leather because of its unsaturated double bond content. This study aimed to use the waste protein from leather shaving and trimming outputs as a good alternative source in preparation of fat liquor cum retanning agent for reducing the pollution and to have better value addition to these wastes. Isolated collagen hydrolysate emulsified with hydrogenated castor and amino functional silicone oils was investigated for the leather production on the way of sustainability of leather industry both by evaluating the tannery wastes and with a single chemical.

2.1.5 Finishing

The hydrolyzed feather can be used as one of the ingredients in the preparation of glue, and film. [26]

2.2 Benefits of Using Natural Polymers for Leather

Using natural polymers for leather processing offers several benefits: First, natural polymers such as chitosan and starch offer a more sustainable and environmentally-friendly alternative to petroleum-based tanning agents. By utilizing renewable resources like chitosan, keratin, carbohydrase the leather industry can reduce its reliance on non-renewable sources and contribute to the overall goal of sustainability

2.3 Comparison of Natural and Synthetic Polymers in Leather Processing

While synthetic polymers have been widely used in leather processing, natural polymers like chitosan offer unique advantages. Unlike synthetic polymers, natural polymers are derived from renewable resources and are biodegradable and compostable. This makes them more environmentally friendly and helps in addressing the challenge of waste disposal. Furthermore, natural polymers can be chemically modified and blended with other biodegradable polymers, plasticizers, and active fillers to enhance their performance in various applications.

In the leather industry, chitosan has been found to have multiple uses, such as a retanning agent and an antimicrobial coating.

2.4 Environmental Impact of Natural Polymers

Using natural polymers like chitosan in leather processing can have a positive environmental impact. Unlike synthetic polymers, which are derived from non-renewable resources and contribute to pollution and waste, chitosan is obtained from renewable sources and is biodegradable. This means that when chitosan-coated leather products reach the end of their lifecycle, they can easily decompose, reducing their environmental footprint. Furthermore, chitosan can also contribute to the reduction of hazardous chemicals in leather processing. Traditional tanning agents often contain harmful substances such as chromium salts, which pose a risk to human health and the environment. By using chitosan as a natural polymer for leather processing, the reliance on these harmful chemicals can be minimized, creating a safer and more sustainable leather.

2.5 Challenges in Using Natural Polymers for Leather Processing

Natural polymers used as an alternative of processing materials. But in most processing stages such as soaking, unhairing, bating stages they are converted to enzymatic solution which is costly. In addition in tanning stage starch cannot be used as tanning material directly it reacts with aldehyde and then applied to specific function here cost and properties of material have incomparable effect with chrome tanning. Keratinous materials as filler and finishing material use complicated production processes. In general natural polymers function as alternative processing materials but further improvement on the manufacturing technique should be done.

3. Future of Leather Processing with Natural Polymers

Despite the numerous benefits of using natural polymers in leather processing, there are still some challenges that need to be addressed. One such challenge is the cost. Natural polymers, although abundant in nature, can sometimes be more expensive to produce and acquire compared to synthetic alternatives. This can pose a barrier for smaller leather manufacturers who may have limited budgets.

4. Conclusion, Recommendation and Prospective of Natural Polymer in Leather Processing

Leather industry is the most polluting industry ever. Eco-friendly remedies of its processing play a lot. Among them protease and carbohydrase enzymes for soaking and cleaning, keratin/keratins for unhairing, starch for tanning, starch and keratinous matters for filling and keratin for glue and film formation of finishing. In general even if natural polymers extraction mechanism and enzyme usage is costly it is the recommended processing mechanism.

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